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Editorial

Launching the Georgian Medical Journal: Transparency, Editorial Standards, and the Foundations of a New Open-Access Platform

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ABSTRACT

This editorial documents the development and launch of the Georgian Medical Journal (GMJ), a new open-access, peer-reviewed medical journal established in 2025. It reports the journal's initial performance across Volume 1, Issue 1, including submission volume, acceptance and rejection rates, authorship diversity, and content scope. The editorial describes the implementation of international editorial standards, including adherence to CONSORT, STROBE, PRISMA, CARE, and SQUIRE guidelines, in alignment with COPE and ICMJE recommendations. It further describes GMJ's integrated knowledge translation strategy, including 100% podcast coverage of all published articles across seven global platforms. Current limitations—including the absence of indexing in major databases and the use of interim DOI assignment via Zenodo—are explicitly acknowledged, alongside a defined roadmap for indexing and editorial expansion. GMJ is established as a transparent, regionally anchored, and internationally oriented platform, complementary to existing Georgian medical publications, and committed to contributing to equitable global scientific publishing.

Keywords: *medical publishing; open access; peer review; editorial transparency; scholarly communication; indexing strategy; knowledge translation; Georgia; scientific publishing; DOAJ; Crossref; scholarly journal development*

INTRODUCTION

The global landscape of medical publishing is undergoing rapid transformation, with increasing emphasis on open access, transparency, and regional equity in knowledge production. Despite this progress, many countries, including Georgia, remain underrepresented in indexed scientific literature, with limited access to independent and internationally aligned publication platforms.

When the first manuscript was submitted to the Georgian Medical Journal in late 2025, the challenge was clear: to establish a journal without citation history, indexing, or institutional legacy, while ensuring

full alignment with international standards of scientific publishing. The aim was to build a rigorous, independent, and open-access journal grounded in the realities of Georgia’s health system and capable of contributing to global scientific discourse.

Georgian clinicians, researchers, and public health professionals require a credible, outward-facing platform that enables the dissemination of locally generated evidence while meeting international expectations for methodological quality, transparency, and editorial integrity. Addressing this gap is essential not only for national scientific development, but also for ensuring that regional perspectives are represented within the global health research ecosystem. GMJ is designed to complement, rather than duplicate, existing Georgian medical publications, by providing an open-access, bilingual, internationally aligned platform for peer-reviewed research.

Volume 1, Issue 1 of GMJ is now complete. As noted in the founding editorial of this issue (Pkhakadze, GMJ 2026;1(1):3–7), the journal’s establishment was motivated by a commitment to equity in scientific publishing and to the elevation of Georgian medical research within the international literature. This closing editorial provides a structured and transparent account of the journal’s initial performance, including submission metrics, authorship patterns, content scope, and operational limitations, alongside a forward-looking assessment of future development.

1. EDITORIAL PERFORMANCE AND SUBMISSION OUTCOMES

Between October 2025 and March 2026, the Georgian Medical Journal received 28 manuscript submissions through its open submission portal. Each submission underwent structured editorial desk screening for scope, methodological integrity, and reporting quality. Manuscripts meeting initial criteria proceeded to double-anonymised peer review by a minimum of two independent reviewers, applying internationally recognised reporting standards (CONSORT, STROBE, PRISMA, CARE, SQUIRE) in alignment with COPE and ICMJE recommendations for ethical editorial practice.

Table 1. Submission and Publication Outcomes, Volume 1, Issue 1

Metric	Value	Metric	Value
Submissions received	28	Submission period	Oct 2025 – Mar 2026
Articles accepted & published	16	Acceptance rate	57.1%
Manuscripts: revise and resubmit	10	Non-acceptance rate	42.9%
Rejected outright (desk + post-review)	2	Authors confirming resubmission	10 / 10 (100%)
Total pages published (Issue 1)	248	DOIs assigned	16 (Zenodo, interim)
Total unique authors	38	Countries represented	5
Institutions represented	15	Podcast episodes produced	16 / 16 (100%)

The non-acceptance rate of 42.9% across all 28 submissions reflects a deliberate editorial policy that prioritises methodological rigour, reporting quality, and scientific credibility over publication volume. Importantly, all 10 manuscripts receiving a revise-and-resubmit decision have confirmed resubmission intent; these are classified as deferred rather than rejected. Editorial decisions were guided by quality thresholds rather than output targets, ensuring that acceptance was contingent on adherence to international standards.

2. AUTHORSHIP AND INSTITUTIONAL REPRESENTATION

Issue 1 brings together 38 authors from 15 institutions across 5 countries. This geographic and institutional diversity was not engineered through solicitation campaigns or paid outreach; all 28 manuscripts were received through the open submission portal without direct outreach to authors.

Table 2. Contributing Countries and Authors, Volume 1, Issue 1

Country	Institution(s)	Author(s)
United Kingdom	Independent contributor	Owen Thomas

India	Batumi Shota Rustaveli University (Georgia-based)	Sharvari Patil
Morocco	Military Teaching Hospital Mohammed V; University Mohammed V, Rabat	Kassa Boukat, El Hammoumi, Benameur, Kabiri
Israel	Hebrew University of Jerusalem; Shaare Zedek Medical Center	Davarashvili, Asher
Georgia	11 institutions — 3 cities (see below)	31 authors

Georgian institutions represented in Issue 1:

- Batumi Shota Rustaveli State University, Batumi
- Avicenna Batumi Medical University, Batumi
- Akaki Tsereteli State University, Kutaisi
- David Tvildiani Medical University (DTMU), Tbilisi
- Public Health Institute of Georgia (PHIG), Tbilisi
- Tbilisi State Medical University, Tbilisi
- New Vision University, Tbilisi
- Georgian Technical University, Tbilisi
- European University, Tbilisi
- David Aghmashenebeli University of Georgia, Tbilisi
- Georgian-Italian Clinic, Tbilisi

The geographic distribution of submissions, spanning Batumi, Kutaisi, and Tbilisi, alongside contributions from the United Kingdom, Morocco, Israel, and India, indicates that GMJ is addressing a structural gap in regional scientific publishing. These submission patterns reflect genuine demand for an independent, internationally aligned publication platform within and beyond Georgia.

3. CONTENT PROFILE AND SCHOLARLY SCOPE

Issue 1 spans a deliberately broad scope of medical scholarship, reflecting the journal’s founding commitment to the full spectrum of evidence-based medicine and public health practice.

Table 3. Article Types and Content Scope, Volume 1, Issue 1

Article Type	Count	Topics Covered
Original Research	8	Cardiovascular surgery, sports cardiology, balneotherapy (×2), vestibular neurogenetics, pharmacovigilance, AI in clinical communication
Editorials and Policy Forum	4	Palliative care policy, IT governance in healthcare, NCD prevention education, founding editorial
Systematic Reviews	2	Metabolic dysfunction and acne severity; infant formula food safety governance
Case Reports (CARE-compliant)	2	Hybrid coronary revascularisation in an octogenarian; sleeve gastrectomy in Type 1 diabetes
Total	16	Pages 3–248 38 authors 15 institutions 5 countries

Every article carries a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), is preserved through PKP Preservation Network, LOCKSS, and CLOCKSS, and is published open access under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0). Submissions in both Georgian and English were welcomed from the first day of operation.

4. KNOWLEDGE TRANSLATION AND DIGITAL DISSEMINATION STRATEGY

From the outset, GMJ recognised that publication alone is insufficient for knowledge translation in a region where audio consumption of health information is growing rapidly. The Georgian Medical

Journal Podcast was established as an integral component of the journal's dissemination strategy, not as an afterthought.

Table 4. Podcast Coverage, Volume 1, Issue 1

Podcast Metric	Value
Total episodes produced (Issue 1)	16 episodes (#32–#47)
Articles with dedicated episodes	16 / 16 (100% coverage)
Streaming platforms	7 platforms
Spotify	open.spotify.com/show/33U05xcBx4ZERFpwppky7d
Apple Podcasts	podcasts.apple.com/fr/podcast/the-georgia-medical-journal-podcast/id1879124703
YouTube	youtube.com/@GeorgianMedicalJournal
Amazon Music	music.amazon.fr/podcasts/4853e78c-2d47-454e-ba85-2e0927829b9f/the-georgian-medical-journal-podcast
Castbox / Goodpods / Pocket Casts	castbox.fm/vh/7075396 goodpods.com/podcasts/...723887 pca.st/1krb6adq

Achieving 100% podcast coverage of Issue 1, with one dedicated episode per published article distributed across seven global platforms, represents an integrated model of knowledge translation that is rarely implemented at journal launch. This approach reflects a strategic commitment to accessibility, extending the reach of scientific outputs beyond traditional academic readership to clinicians, students, and the broader public, thereby strengthening the societal impact of published research.

5. CURRENT STATUS, LIMITATIONS, AND INDEXING STRATEGY

Scientific integrity requires explicit acknowledgement of current limitations. GMJ is in its first year of operation and is not yet indexed in MEDLINE, Scopus, Web of Science, or PubMed Central. All editorial processes, however, have been designed and implemented in accordance with international best practices, aligned with COPE and ICMJE standards. DOIs are currently assigned through Zenodo, a recognised open-science repository operated by CERN, as an interim measure during the journal's initial development phase.

These are structural constraints inherent to new journals, not reflections of editorial standards. GMJ's policies, peer review processes, reporting standards, and archiving infrastructure have been built to meet the requirements of the indexing bodies being pursued. The timeline is defined:

- DOAJ application, submitted immediately following Issue 1 closure
- Crossref membership, registration underway; 20-article threshold met
- PubMed Central, application to follow DOAJ approval
- Retroactive DOI migration to Crossref for all Issue 1 articles
- Expanded international peer reviewer network, active recruitment for Issue 2

Issue 2 is currently in active development, with 15 manuscripts under peer review. All 10 authors who received revise-and-resubmit decisions for Issue 1 have confirmed resubmission. As submission volume increases, the journal aims to maintain a target rejection rate of 40–50%.

6. PEER REVIEW PROCESS AND REVIEWER ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

All manuscripts submitted to GMJ undergo a structured editorial process consisting of initial desk evaluation followed by double-anonymised peer review conducted by a minimum of two independent reviewers. The journal adheres to COPE and ICMJE recommendations and established reporting guidelines including CONSORT, STROBE, PRISMA, CARE, and SQUIRE.

The Editorial Office expresses its sincere appreciation to the reviewers who contributed to Volume 1, Issue 1. Reviewers were selected on the basis of subject-matter expertise and institutional affiliation, drawing on both national and international experts. Their contributions were essential in evaluating methodological rigour, reporting quality, and scientific relevance, ensuring that editorial decisions were based on transparent and objective criteria.

GMJ recognises peer review as a fundamental component of scholarly publishing and remains committed to strengthening its reviewer network, enhancing transparency, and maintaining the highest standards of editorial independence and research integrity.

7. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND FORWARD OUTLOOK

The publication of Volume 1, Issue 1 reflects the collective effort of peer reviewers, authors, and the editorial team. The contributions of 38 authors across 15 institutions and 5 countries, together with the voluntary engagement of peer reviewers, were essential to maintaining editorial standards under the operational constraints of an inaugural issue. The journal is grateful to all who submitted work, participated in peer review, and supported the development of this platform.

The Georgian Medical Journal is independent, peer-reviewed, and fully open access. It publishes in both Georgian and English and is designed to serve the Georgian medical and scientific community while contributing to the international research landscape. With the completion of Volume 1, Issue 1, GMJ enters a phase of consolidation and expansion, with a defined focus on indexing, peer review capacity, and international visibility.

Conflict of Interest: The author is Editor-in-Chief of the Georgian Medical Journal. This editorial was handled in accordance with standard editorial procedures for editor-authored content, with oversight by an independent associate editor.

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